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DELIVERABLE REPORT

Production of material samples of carbon-based composites and metal-diamond composites

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ABSTRACT

The aim of task 14.4 within WP14 is to develop and industrialize materials for extreme thermal management. This is done in collaboration with two industrial partners, RHP (AT) and Brevetti Bizz (IT). The materials produced include composites combining the properties of metals and ceramics with those of carbon allotropes like graphite and diamond. Advanced manufacturing techniques such as spark plasma sintering, additive manufacturing, rapid hot pressing, are adopted. This report documents the production of samples made of ceramic-graphite and copper-diamond, produced for applications in particle beam intercepting devices and luminescence screens. These samples will be tested in the scope of WP17 “PowerMat”, at CERN, GSI, PoliMi, PoliTo and other international partners.

ARIES Consortium, 2018

For more information on ARIES, its partners and contributors please see <http://aries.web.cern.ch>

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Delivery Slip

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Executive summary

This report documents the production of material samples of carbon-based and metal-diamond composites. In terms of quantity, the goal of the deliverable was the production of at least 50 carbon-based composites at Brevetti Bizz (IT) and 30 samples of metal-diamond at RHP (AT), 20 of which to be used for high-energy impact tests and 10 for luminescence studies.

The due date for this deliverable was month 24; however, the samples produced are tested in the scope of WP17 of ARIES (PowerMat). This deliverable was anticipated by 10 months to synchronize with the planning of WP17, which included tests in the HiRadMat facility at CERN already in autumn 2017, and additional studies at CERN, GSI, PoliTo and PoliMi in 2018.

Sample production took place during the second half of 2017 and the first half of 2018. The samples were produced in different shapes, as a function of the testing requirements of WP17, and with advanced techniques such as Spark-Plasma Sintering (SPS) as well as Additive Manufacturing (AD). The quantities produced exceeded the initial target of the deliverable, but are still within the total production objectives of the 4-year project.

1. Introduction

The scope of the task 14.4 within ARIES WP14 is to realize materials for extreme thermal management applications. These materials, produced by the industrial partners Brevetti Bizz (IT) and RHP (AT), can be tailored to achieve high thermal, electrical and mechanical performance, as well as low density. This combination of properties is required in the construction of particle accelerator components such as beam intercepting devices (collimators, targets and dumps); however, similar requirements are also shared by numerous industrial applications, involving for example heat dissipation and cooling devices, aerospace components, energy production, etc. Industrialization of the materials developed is, in fact, an important objective of the work package: feasibility of production for large-scale components will be proved by realizing one composite piece of complex shape, with big dimensions and tight tolerance. Task 14.4 also includes the development of metal-diamond specimens for application in luminescence screens, as well the realization of superconductive thin films in MgB_2 by additive manufacturing.

The deliverable documented in this report included the production of the material specimens summarized in Table 1.

Table 1 – Production requirements for D14.3

N. samples	Description	Producer
50	Carbon-based specimens for collimators	Brevetti Bizz
20	Metal-diamond specimens for collimators	RHP
10	Metal-diamond specimens for luminescence screens	RHP

This deliverable was due by month 24; however, the samples produced are tested in the scope of WP17 of ARIES (PowerMat). The deliverable was thus anticipated by 10 months to synchronize with the planning of WP17, which included tests in the HiRadMat facility at CERN already in autumn 2017, and additional studies at CERN, GSI, PoliTo and PoliMi in 2018.

Table 2 summarizes the samples produced to achieve the deliverable production targets, also providing information on the material compositions and envisaged testing methods.

Table 2 – Specimens produced for D14.3

Description	N. samples required	N. samples produced	Composition and envisaged testing method
Carbon-based specimens for collimators	50	36	Ceramic-graphite for thermomechanical characterization at CERN
		25	Molybdenum-graphite for dynamic tests at PoliTo
Metal-diamond specimens for collimators	20	11	Copper-diamond for beam impact tests at CERN HiRadMat facility
		17	Copper-diamond for thermomechanical characterization at CERN
Metal-diamond specimens for luminescence screens	10	10	Diamond-based composites with different metallic substrates for testing at CERN and GSI

The realization of each sample is documented in the following paragraphs, also including details of the production techniques, the materials adopted and the shape of the specimens.

2. Copper-Diamond samples for particle beam impact tests in HiRadMat at CERN

Copper-diamond (CuCD) is a composite material developed with the goal of combining the main advantages of its two constituents: copper and diamond. Its thermal conductivity is considerably improved as respect to pure copper by addition of diamond. Diamonds strongly reduce the thermal expansion coefficient and the density of the composite with respect to the pure metal as well [1].

The CuCD grade presented in this report (RHP3025-01:10), manufactured by RHP (AT), is produced by Spark-Plasma Sintering (SPS) using a compact of cold pressed powders, also known as “green”, at 35 MPa. The reached temperature which is slightly below the melting point of copper (1000-1050 °C), is maintained for 1-4 hours, with a successive controlled cooling down to 400°C. The standard powder mixture is made of diamond particles, carbide-forming elements and copper powder. Mono-modal and multi-modal diamond mixtures were adopted. The process is conducted under dry hydrogen gas atmosphere. The machine adapted at RHP for the production of the material is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1 – Left: SPS machine at RHP. Right: high-temperature sintering.

The grade RHP3025-01:10 of CuCD was selected to be tested in the “Multimat” experiment at the CERN HiRadMat facility [2] in October 2017. The goal of the experiment was to test 18 different materials under high intensity proton pulses of 440 GeV/c, exceeding the energy density expected in HL-LHC, and to acquire their dynamic response by means of embarked and remote instrumentation. The material rod-like specimens were positioned on a rotatable sample holder (Figure 2) inserted in a tank under inert atmosphere [3].

Figure 2 – Multimat rotatable sample holder, hosting rods made of 18 different materials.

11 rods of CuCD grade RHP3025-01:10 were produced for Multimat in July 2017 (Figure 3). The rod dimensions are 250x10x10 mm³. The density of the samples is about 5.7 g/cm³, slightly higher than what is typically considered for collimator applications (5.2-5.4 g/cm³).

Figure 3 – Left: 11 rod-like samples of CuCD grade RHP3025-01:10 produced for Multimat. Right: dimensional details, 6 samples out of 11 are shown.

The Multimat experiment was a success. Collected data are encouraging, matching well the results of advanced computations, when previously unknown material properties are plugged back into numerical models [4]. A large amount of information is being treated within ARIES WP17 and will help improving constitutive models for the less known composite materials.

3. Copper-Diamond and Ceramic-Graphite samples for thermophysical characterization at CERN

One of the goals of ARIES WP17 is to develop constitutive models for the composite materials treated in this report. Tests under direct beam impact, such as those described in section 2, must be complemented by a set of measurements of the thermomechanical and physical properties such as mechanical strength, thermal and electrical conductivity, thermal diffusivity, density, specific heat, coefficient of thermal expansion. These tests are typically performed as a function of temperature, to cover operative conditions of particle accelerator components, as well as of industrial applications such as heat dissipation and energy production. The CERN Mechanical Laboratory, in the Engineering Department, Mechanical and Materials Engineering group (EN-MME), is equipped for a comprehensive characterization in static conditions.

This chapter describes the production of samples of CuCD grade RHP3025-01:10 and of a novel ceramic-graphite (CerGr) composite for the thermomechanical characterization at the EN-MME MechLab.

CuCD RHP3025-01:10 is the grade described in section 2 and tested in Multimat. A complete characterization allows reconstructing the material models and simulating the beam impact scenario tested in HiRadMat, to prove the model validity and improve it if necessary. CerGr, on the other hand, is a graphitic material reinforced with a carbide phase to increase the through-plane properties of oriented graphite. It is realized by Brevetti Bizz with the SPS technique. This report does not include further details on the composition and sintering process, as the material disclosure is currently being investigated by the Knowledge Transfer group at CERN and by the producer.

The shape of the samples produced was variable, as each testing method requires a different geometry; also, while CuCD is isotropic, CerGr is a transversally isotropic material, and requires at least twice as many samples, to measure the properties in the two principal directions. The number and geometry of the samples produced is reported below:

Ceramic-graphite (36 samples in total), production period March 2018

- n. 4 discs D10x2mm in Longitudinal plane for thermal conductivity and diffusivity
- n. 3 discs D10x6mm in Transversal plane for thermal conductivity and diffusivity
- n. 3 bars 25x5x5mm in Longitudinal plane for coefficient of thermal expansion
- n. 4 bars 15x5x5mm in Transversal plane for coefficient of thermal expansion
- n. 6 bars 55x10x5 mm in Longitudinal plane for bending strength
- n. 6 bars 25x10x5 mm in Transversal plane for bending strength
- n. 3 bars 45x5x4 mm in Longitudinal plane for electrical conductivity
- n. 3 bars 25x5x5 mm in Transversal plane for electrical conductivity
- n. 4 discs D5x1mm in Long. Or Trans. plane for specific heat

Copper-diamond (17 samples in total), production period June 2018

- n. 4 discs D10x5mm for thermal conductivity and diffusivity

- n. 3 bars 25x5x5mm for coefficient of thermal expansion
- n. 5 bars 35x5x5 mm for bending strength and electrical conductivity
- n. 3 blocks 4.5x5x5mm for thermal conductivity and diffusivity in the pressing direction
- n. 1 block 20x15x5 for SEY observations
- n. 1 bar 35x5x1.5 to be further cut for specific heat

The samples of the two materials produced for thermomechanical and electrical characterization are shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4 – Top left: 36 samples of CerGr. Top right: CuCD plate with samples cut by water-jet. Bottom: 17 samples of CuCD extracted from the plate. All specimens are for thermophysical characterization at the CERN EN-MME Mechanical Laboratory.

4. Metal-Diamond samples for luminescence screens

The addition of diamond particles to metallic substrates is a technique exploitable in the construction of beam instruments such as luminescence screens. Diamonds act as scintillators upon interaction with incident high-energy beam, allowing to derive useful information on the shape of the beam. Several parameters must be taken in consideration while developing a luminescence target of this kind. Diamond size has an influence on the acquisition resolution of the incident beam. Density and atomic number of the metallic substrate control the interaction between the beam and the target. Finally, a robust substrate is necessary to maximize the target resistance to induced heat and sputtering damage.

The production of samples for luminescence studies took place at RHP. The production technique involves induction hot pressing, and is sketched in Figure 5.

Figure 5 – Production of luminescence targets at RHP by induction hot pressing. Configuration on the right is optimized to double the number of specimens produced during every machine cycle.

Ten luminescence samples have been produced so far at RHP. Six of those were produced in summer 2017 for tests at GSI; four additional samples, produced in April 2018, were tested at CERN HiRadMat by the Beams department, Beam Instrumentation group. The specimens produced investigated different combinations of substrate materials (Ti and Al alloys, Ti composites, OFE Cu) as well as diamond powder size (10-45 micron), type and purity. Other tested parameters were the sintering dwell time, temperature and applied pressure.

The samples are discs with diameter 36 mm and thickness 1 mm. The targets tested in HiRadMat were then cut to a rectangular or square shape. The ten specimens are shown in Figure 6 and Figure 7.

Figure 6 – Six samples for luminescence studies for tests at GSI. Macroscopic and microscopic configuration.

Figure 7 – Four samples for tests at CERN HiRadMat. Top: back face, showing the metallic substrate. Bottom: front face, showing the diamond layer. Courtesy of S. Burger, CERN.

5. Molybdenum-Graphite samples for dynamic tests at PoliTo

The material characterization taking place at CERN EN-MME Laboratory, and mentioned in section 3, is limited to static tests. The influence of the strain rate on the material response to a dynamic load cannot be investigated with the available instruments. To explore this dependence, a dedicated setup must be put in place, involving dynamic characterization methods such as Hopkinson bar [5], Taylor tests, flyer plates, etc.

Politecnico di Torino (PoliTo), a participant to ARIES within WP17, is equipped for such measurements. Material samples are tested with a Split-Hopkinson pressure bar setup (SHPB). The setup makes use of a gas gun to direct a striker, at high velocity, against an input bar. The compressive wave generated travels through the bar and is transmitted to the specimen and to an output bar. Both input and output bars are equipped with strain gauges and, knowing the density and elastic modulus of the bars and of the specimens, it is possible to reconstruct the strain generated on the sample at strain rates up to 10^3 - 10^4 s⁻¹. The setup is shown in Figure 8.

Figure 8 – Top: functioning of a SHPB for tests of specimens under compression at high speed. Bottom: experimental setup at PoliTo.

The samples necessary for the dynamic characterization must be very small and with threaded extremities, to connect them with the input and output bars. Figure 9 reports the dimensional requirements for the specimens.

Figure 9 – SHPB sample dimensional requirements.

Molybdenum-graphite (MoGr) [6], produced at Brevetti Bizz, is one of the composites characterized within ARIES WP17. The composite is processed by SPS with sintering temperatures exceeding 2600 °C, melting the molybdenum carbide and enhancing the graphitization of the material. Figure 10 schematizes the SPS machine adapted at Brevetti Bizz to sinter the material.

Figure 10 – SPS machine at Brevetti Bizz.

Brevetti Bizz produced in December 2017, 25 specimens of MoGr grade MG-6403Fc for dynamic testing at PoliTo. In spite of the expected difficulties in the realizing the thread of so small graphitic samples, MoGr proved to be easily machinable and the result obtained by Brevetti Bizz is excellent. The specimen production is documented in Figure 11 and Figure 12.

Figure 11 – 25 MoGr threaded samples for dynamic tests at PoliTo, produced by Brevetti Bizz.

Figure 12 – A MoGr threaded sample in detail.

The samples were also analysed at CERN, before shipping to PoliTo, to observe the possible presence and distribution of defects and carbide clusters. This was done by means of a new X-ray tomograph available at EN-MME [7]. Videos and images were captured for each sample, and will be

crosschecked with the post-experiment images to investigate possible fracture patterns. An example of the tomography is shown in Figure 13.

Figure 13 – Tomography of a MoGr threaded sample. The colour scale is related to the size of carbide clusters.

6. Conclusions and future plans

The production targets for D14.3 were reached in month 14, ten months earlier than the due date of month 24. This was necessary to synchronize the activities of WP14 with the planning of WP17, within which the samples are characterized. As shown in table 2, the quantity of targets was in fact slightly exceeded and includes some spare sample to increase the data statistics of each test. The industrial partners, RHP and Brevetti Bizz, proved to be very reactive, and managed to realize in a short time specimens of very complex shapes.

In terms of planning for the task 14.4 of WP14, the situation is good, and some production targets for the full 4-year project have already been reached. Some others, such as the realization of superconductive MgB₂ films on metallic substrates, were not in the scope of this deliverable, but the R&D has already started and we expect to have the first samples in the second half of 2018. Production targets to be achieved by 2021 are summarized in Table 3, together with the advancement status of each item.

Table 3 – Production objectives for task 14.4 (due date is month 48)

N. samples	Description	Producer	Level of completion
30	MgB ₂ on metal substrate samples	RHP	0% – R&D ongoing
50	Copper-diamond samples for collimators		50%
40	Metal-diamond samples for luminescence screens		25%
50	Carbide-graphite or metal-graphite samples for collimators	Brevetti Bizz	100%
1	Large size block of carbide graphite or metal-graphite with tight mechanical tolerances to proof industrialization		0% – R&D ongoing

7. References

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Annex: Glossary

Acronym	Definition
PoliMi	Politecnico di Milano
PoliTo	Politecnico di Torino
CuCD	Copper-Diamond
SPS	Spark-Plasma Sintering
CerGr	Ceramic-Graphite
EN-MME	CERN Engineering Department, Mechanical and Materials Engineering Group
SPHB	Split-Hopkinson pressure bar
MoGr	Molybdenum-Graphite